

Innovativeness as a competitive advantage for SMMEs in South Africa

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Digital business innovation can result in a competitive advantage for small, medium and micro-organizations SMMEs. This study explores the obstacles SMMEs face in South Africa. Registered SMMEs served as the study population, and a non-probability sample was selected for in-depth interviews to obtain the qualitative data. The findings indicate that SMMEs adopt innovation for management support, funding, employee motivation, staff education and training, and internal environment commitment. SMMEs support employees' innovation efforts, and find ways to increase the flow of financing for innovation implementation and commit to creating a healthy workplace culture. It is important for SMMEs to be competitive and augment their ability to innovate businesses, products, processes, markets and human capital skills through education and training to be able to stay abreast with new developments in the field of digital business.

Keywords: competitive advantage, innovation, SMMEs, South Africa

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Introduction

Many developing countries, especially in Africa acknowledge the significance of small, medium and micro-organizations (SMMEs) as a stakeholder in a country's economy (Nodira & Rashid 2022, Watkins 2012). Many SMMEs need to survive and flourish in the digital economy and the evolving market conditions. It forces SMMEs to deploy novel products that are efficient and tailored to their particular needs and business models. SMMEs form a significant sector in the economy of any country, making up over 95 percent of all enterprises and creating an additional 60 percent of all employment (OECD 2018). Because SMMEs are crucial to developing economies, it is necessary to deliberate their impact (Chimucheka & Mandipaka 2015). The role of SMMEs is reflected in the creation of employment and growth of the trade balance, which promotes national economic advancement. Innovativeness is crucial for SMME growth and acquiring a competitive advantage (Oduntan 2014). A lack of creativity may be why many SMMEs still need to progress past the early stages of their existence (SADC 2019). Supporting the growth of SMMEs has been a top priority during and COVID-19 post-pandemic. Over 140m SMMEs in 130 countries employed 65 percent of the total labor force (World Bank 2016). During this tragedy, the South African government assisted SMMEs through various financial, technical, and research initiatives (Coad et al.

2020). SMMEs need more fresh ideas, which make it possible for them to manage their business plans that have already been launched successfully. Moreover, SMMEs' competitiveness can increase due to innovation adoption despite the difficulties SMMEs encounter with technology adoption and financial access (Brodny et al. 2023). SMMEs are increasingly a focus of many nations because SMMEs are essential to the economy of almost all nations. SMMEs can be useful in leveraging employment generation, given South Africa's 25 percent unemployment rate (Olawale & Garwe 2010). Any research on enhancing the competitiveness of SMMEs is essential in today's economic climate.

However, SMMEs face obstacles such as competition from within and beyond the nation. Innovation is the key to boosting growth and giving SMMEs a sustained competitive advantage (Oduntan 2014). Innovation can boost organizational growth, which creates a long-lasting competitive advantage on both the internal micro-level (market-focused) and the external macro-level (international context) marketplaces (Setyawati et al. 2023). Because adopting new digital strategies is essential for achieving organizational competitiveness, this study yields insights into how SMMEs can do so.

Literature Review

A comprehensive review of scholarly research on innovation and how it provides SMMEs a competitive advantage was undertaken. The aim was to determine how scholars have dealt with the concepts of innovation and competitive advantage. The innovation process is driven by various drivers, some of which are internal to an organization (SMMEs in this case) and others from the outside world (Cankar & Petkovsek 2013). Internal drivers are strategy, organizational climate, strategic leadership, entrepreneurship, and organizational resources, and the external drivers include political, social, economic, technological, supplier, and customer. These drivers are depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Drivers of Innovation

Source: Adapted from Cankar & Petkovsek (2013), Wang et al. (2016)

External Environment

An organization's external environment consists of diverse demands and factors that may impact the organization. However, an organization cannot directly control the external environment and must adapt to it (Wang et al. 2016). The external environment comprises political, economic, ecological, sociological, and technological influences. By passing the necessary laws, policies, and regulations, the government significantly influences fostering and enabling of organizational environments (Proctor 2013). The goals of industrial policymaking should be to achieve an accelerated pace of competitive and sustainable industrial growth within a functional framework of increased market orientation and private-sector-led development (Liu et al. 2015). This is true for any innovation-driven economy. The availability of basic physical infrastructure such as electricity, transportation, telecommunications, institutional infrastructure, mechanisms for mobilizing 'investible resources', and providing institutional support for developing sustainable innovation capacity are all examples of enabling environmental factors (Park et al. 2019).

The cost of resources for an organization and its consumer demand for services and goods are affected by economic growth, interest rates, currency rates, inflation rates, and other factors (Laforet 2011). Therefore, organizations may pursue innovation to combat the effects of one or all of the elements that threaten an organization's success over the long and short terms. Pressure is on the shoulders of management to reduce costs, boost efficiency, and enhance results, fueling innovation.

Social elements are thought of as factors outside of an organization's control. Thus, only so many organizations can do to impact it. However, using innovation, social factors such as changing demographics, diseases, poverty, and hunger can be effectively managed and controlled (Lee et al. 2012). The adoption of innovation in organizations is driven mainly by pressures for better service and quality (Laforet 2011).

Technology advancement that affects an organization's automation success and potential creates a fertile environment for innovation activities that create new or enhanced goods and services (Lewrick et al. 2012). Khilji et al. (2012) find that technology and automation could affect the demand for services and goods, cut costs, and foster innovation. Technological innovation has the potential to strongly influence or drive future innovation.

The importance of suppliers and consumers in driving product and service innovation was emphasized (Agolla 2015). An organization's products can be improved with the assistance of suppliers and consumers. Organizations can foster innovation if they have close relationships with their consumers (Laforet 2011). Partnerships between consumers and suppliers bring significant organizational advantages (Tsekouras et al. 2011).

Internal Environment

The internal drivers under scrutiny are organizational strategy, organizational climate, culture, strategic leadership, entrepreneurship, and management support. One of the main forces behind successful innovation is an organizational strategy, which facilitates integration, consistency, and effective and straightforward communication of the plan to the organization's members (Dani & Gandhi 2022). The importance of innovation inside an organization must be communicated, and management must decide how to employ technology and apply the right performance indicators to achieve performance improvements (Pikkarainen et al. 2018). In a related study, Dobni and Klassen (2015) claim that defining what innovation means to the organization, or the areas of concentration in terms of innovation, is the first stage in developing an innovation strategy. An organization can define its target areas for innovation by identifying the drivers of innovation demands. To get employee buy-in, the innovation strategy must expressly state how it will convey to employees the value of innovation and reflect the importance management accords it. Dobni and Klassen (2015) contributed to this discussion by stating that for employees to act creatively and innovatively, the organization must ensure that they are aware of the vision and mission of the organization, as well as the differences between the present situation and these

two goals. Innovation is directly connected to the success of an organization (Murray et al. 2010). Through this, organizations can produce successful results and strengthen their competitive advantage.

The perception of an organization's internal and external stakeholders can be used to operationally measure the organizational climate, which can be defined as the emotions, attitudes, and behavioral inclinations that characterize organizational effectiveness. Saunila and Ukko (2012) refer to this as an atmosphere marked by worker cohesion and support, as well as by the inherent recognition of temporary workers, and encourages employees to devote time and energy to innovation. Organizational culture is the pattern of shared values, beliefs, and accepted standards that influence behavior (Murray et al. 2010). Ideologies are tied to new ways of thinking, while norms, values, and expectations are related to cultural innovation (Johannessen & Skaalsvik 2015). The top echelons of an organization should foster a culture in which employees are recognized for their contributions toward innovation. An organization's climate reflects the shared knowledge and meaning embodied in its culture (Choi & Park 2014). An open organizational culture is one of the essential prerequisites for an innovative organization's success (Dani & Gandhi 2022). Thus, management should start by supporting innovation.

Creative businesses seek radical change to boost performance and frequently employ strategic leadership to realize creative direction and innovative potential. How well these areas are accomplished will determine how successful management will be in the long run. Additionally, Dobni and Klassen (2015) show a more direct connection between organizational culture, climate for organizational innovation, and the transformational leadership components of vision, indicating a higher chance of innovative work practices.

Entrepreneurship and innovation go hand-in-hand because innovation is the specialized instrument entrepreneurs use to seize opportunities presented by change for a new organization or service (Santandreu et al. 2013). The process by which employees bring new concepts to the organization is known as entrepreneurial innovation (Dumay et al. 2013). Essential resource for innovation is human capital, which includes people's knowledge, abilities, and experiences. Organizations should invest in human capital by enhancing education and training, providing learning opportunities, and thus fostering the workforce's capacity for innovation. Organizations can enhance their members' talents, which can be extremely important to an organization's innovation. Creativity should be interwoven into the training activities of employees' personal development. As employees produce new information, they create opportunities that enhance the efficiency of an organization (Ruiz-Jimenez et al. 2016).

Management should encourage and support employees' creative ideas and devise ways to modify existing incentives and reward programs to facilitate capitalizing on the benefits of this hold (Proctor 2013). Management fosters knowledge appropriation and acquisition, which may be leveraged to foster innovation inside an organization (Lopez & Esteves 2013). This is true because managers encourage and facilitate innovation.

Innovation and Creation of Competitive Advantage

A combination of formal and informal innovation procedures is often used by better-performing service organizations (Brodny et al. 2023). Amarakoon et al. (2018) postulate that having a culture that encourages employees (internal environment), consumers, and all stakeholders to offer creative ideas is one of the most important elements for innovation implementation. This stresses that management should focus on developing methods of evaluating the efficacy and efficiency of procedures designed to persuade other stakeholders and clients to contribute to developing service solutions (Barrett et al. 2015). An organization's resources should set it apart from its competitors and be challenging to duplicate or replace. Saunila (2014) advises that SMMEs can reap even greater rewards if they investigate the innovation orientation for competitive advantage (Figure 2) and develop new products, processes, markets, and internal communication.

Figure 2: Innovation and Competitive Advantage

Source: Adapted from Aziz & Samad (2016), Zhao (2012)

Innovation is a mental process (Abou-Moghli et al. 2012) that results in the development of a brand-new phenomenon or value addition in the form of a brand-new product, service, or technology. The types of innovation that are appropriate for SMMEs include market innovation (as it relates to the expansion of territorial areas and penetration of market segments); process innovation (purchasing and sales, administration, management, and staff policy); and product innovation (about goods, services, and new ideas) (Aziz & Samad 2016). The competitive tactics, movements, and innovations of competitor brands impact organizations (Kahn 2018). Organizations need help establishing a competitive advantage for survival in these conditions. Strategic management and innovative processes must be coordinated for an organization to have a competitive advantage. Products with a substantial competitive advantage offer consumers high value and foster client loyalty. Notably, a more significant competitive advantage implies that products are challenging rivals to replicate (Zhao 2012). Organizations could succeed in their marketplaces and gain a significant competitive advantage by innovating (Moreno Luzon et al. 2013, Soliman 2013). Greater levels of innovation result in a better competitive advantage, as per their study on food manufacturing SMEs in Malaysia (Aziz & Samad 2016). The favorable impact of innovation on competitive advantage was also found in a study of financial innovation on the competitive advantage of telecommunication organizations in Kenya (Mathenge 2013).

Methodology

Convenience sampling was adopted for this study, and participants had to comply with a set of prerequisites and requirements as set for this study. The intentionally recruited respondents were interviewed in-depth, and data collection continued until participants started repeating themes, where added data collection became superfluous because the information provided was no longer helpful in answering the research question as data saturation was reached. Due to technological saturation, the twelve interviews in this investigation yielded no novel information. The interview transcripts were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-stage technique. Data were examined using Atlas-ti version 8.1. Informed permission, responder anonymity, the protection of participant rights, and confidentiality were also considered in the study as ethical research practices.

Due to time and resource constraints, the focus was on SMMEs in the Ngaka Modiri Molema District. It is crucial to analyze the sampling frame's comprehensiveness and to ensure that the chosen sample accurately represents the target population when assessing a sampling frame. Data were gathered through in-depth interviews. Semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data needed because this method allows participants freedom and flexibility when researching an issue. When necessary, probing questions were utilized to elicit further details or clarity from participants. Semi-structured Zoom

interviews allow for a more thorough investigation to clarify meaning and for recording interviews. Each participant was given an identical set of open-ended inquiries, and they were urged to answer honestly. This study used software and qualitative theme analysis to examine participants' views, deeper understandings, perceptions, and knowledge to ascertain how they provide meaning to a certain phenomenon. The process of selecting themes was the first stage in the qualitative data analysis, followed by giving meaning to the interview schedules. Twelve respondents who are knowledgeable about innovation were subjected to in-depth interviews. The participants' responses were combined into a single transcript before the raw data analysis began. It was simpler to see the answers each of the twelve participants gave to each question. The transcript was then entered into the Atlas.ti program for additional examination.

Credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability were employed as the study's trustworthiness metrics. Credibility was ensured using the following techniques: extended involvement, continual observation, reflexivity, peer participant debriefing, and member check. A member verification process was carried out, and a comprehensive explanation of the research methodology was provided to ensure transferability. To ensure accuracy, the research methodology was carefully documented, and the investigation was tracked in detail. It was vital to ensure that the research findings accurately reflected the data the participants provided without including any of their preferences or personality traits.

Research ethics refers to the code of conduct or anticipated societal norms of behavior of individuals and relationships when conducting a research study. Firstly, SMME collaboration and formal voluntary consent were sought, along with the freedom to withdraw at any time during the process. Secondly, potential respondents were informed in full of the purpose of the study. Thirdly, respondents' identities are to remain anonymous, as was promised. Fourthly, responses are shielded using pseudocodes, all personally identifying information is deleted, and the data gathered is securely stored.

The participants were recruited from the North West province's Central Database of SMMEs. Five proprietors of SMMEs and seven managerial personnel were interviewed. 'SM' was used as a pseudonym for the management staff, and 'SO' was used as a code for the owners of SMMEs, to distinguish between the participants who took part in the study. Table 1 below summarizes the profiles of the research participants and the length of their interviews.

Table 1. Research Participants' Profiles and Interview Duration

<i>No</i>	<i>Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Work Exp (yr)</i>	<i>Qualification</i>	<i>Interview duration (Min)</i>
1	SM1	M	4	Degree	20
2	SM2	F	4	Master	17
3	SM3	F	2	Degree	21
4	SM4	M	4	Master	19
5	SM5	M	4	Degree	19
6	SO1	F	4	Diploma	16
7	SM6	M	4	Diploma	20
8	SO2	M	4	Degree	21
9	SO3	F	4	Diploma	17
10	SO4	M	4	Master	19
11	SO5	M	4	Degree	20
12	SM7	M	3	Degree	18

Results

Themes surfaced throughout the Atlas. Data analysis was used to group the study's findings. They were

organized using the themes and sub-themes from the data analysis. During data analysis, several subthemes arose, including inadequate funding, supplier collaboration, usage of digital business systems, improved internal communication, increased research and development, management support, and employee motivation. Effective and ineffective were the two key themes into which the researchers divided sub-themes. Table 2 below lists the major topics and sub-themes from the study.

Table 2. Themes and Sub-themes from the Study

Themes	Sub-themes
Effective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Adequate funding -Use of digital business systems -Management support -Improve internal communication
Ineffective	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Collaboration with suppliers -Inadequate funding -All departments involved

Utilizing digital business systems, finance, managerial support, improving internal communication, working with suppliers, and teamwork (including all departments) were the subthemes that emerged during data analysis. Effective and ineffective were the two key themes into which the researchers divided sub-themes. Most survey respondents who responded to a discussion designed to uncover innovation issues said there needs to be more funding for successful innovation in SMMEs. Table 3 shows participants' quotes.

Table 3. Participants' Quotes on Challenges affecting Innovation

Pseudonym	Quotes
SM1	We lack funding to purchase research materials.
SM3	There are no research and development facilities such as Wi-Fi and use of latest technology which is most challenging to my organization.
SM5	Employees have no ideas and willingness to innovate.
SO2	Lack of innovative ideas due to the low level of education and training of employees.
SO3	We lack time to research to develop unique products to supply our consumers.
SO5	Availability of time to research new processes and new products from our suppliers.

Clearly, it is challenging to innovate effectively. The main issue is the need for more funds and resources. Innovation has many effects, depending on which SMMEs are involved. While specific organizations use innovation for their production processes rather frequently, others sometimes do so.

Discussion

The study's primary objectives were to examine innovation as a source of competitive advantage for SMMEs and ascertain if SMMEs prioritize innovation for expansion. The themes and subthemes from the study are discussed in the following section. *Collaboration* is essential for the category of product innovation to be used effectively. SMMEs need better teamwork, communication, and creative management. In addition, SMMEs should foster understanding by communicating with one another within the organization. Staff competency, *a lack of managerial support*, and a need for more resources are barriers to innovation. Due to the high costs of process research and development and market

innovation, the cost of innovation can be substantial. Lack of funding is one of the major problems for SMMEs. Another issue is employees' capacity to provide knowledge. Formal employee education and training are difficult for businesses to afford, which limits their capacity to implement innovation. A variety of new products and services were given to entice repeat consumers and maintain competitiveness. Due to the fierce competition from large businesses, most SMME did implement innovation in their organizations. It strengthened and improved internal environments, operational processes, and market innovation. An SMME needs to be sufficiently innovative to offer distinct products.

Innovation is a crucial instrument that SMME forge a competitive edge and capture markets and clients. This means that SMME's success and competitive advantage depend heavily on innovation. One of the leading causes of SMME failure and discontinuity in South Africa is a need for more organizational innovation. However, what is essential is that these innovations support their operational success and competitive advantage.

Conclusion

Innovation is crucial for SMMEs to grow their market share and keep their consumers. It explains introducing and developing new ideas into the market and enhancing a product to set it apart from competitors. Because it helps businesses adapt their products and services to changing consumer tastes and design standards, innovation substantially impacts the competitiveness of SMMEs. This ought to boost earnings, customer loyalty, and sales. Innovative SMMEs are more likely to be competitive and grow and expand than non-innovative ones. SMMEs need to assess their innovation strategies and make sure they invest in R&D, to be able to succeed and gain a competitive advantage. Some SMMEs are aware of the need for innovation for their organization's survival and market expansion, and they realize the necessity to differentiate themselves from their competitors by providing distinctive goods and services. If SMMEs want to expand, they must successfully handle new obstacles. This is due to the fact that one of the main reasons SMME discontinuity occurs is a need for more money for R&D prior to innovation and the expertise necessary to innovate, as innovation is a must for SMME growth and sustainability.

Innovation must be viewed as a requirement if SMMEs are to gain a competitive advantage, survive, and expand. SMMEs must employ innovation in this highly competitive climate, especially when competing with larger organizations that already enjoy significant economies of scale. This means that SMMEs hesitant to implement innovation in this cutthroat environment are unlikely to survive and prosper. SMMEs may be reluctant to innovate and have a high probability of discontinuity. SMMEs may not be innovative since they need more resources for research and development and need to understand what innovation is. This demonstrates that for SMMEs to survive and flourish, owners and managers must invest in research and development, and staff members must improve their education and training to keep up with innovation demands. Since employees provide the information and resources for innovation, which will impact on SMME's competitive advantage, using education, training, and financial resources for research and development can be the ideal solution for SMMEs' competitive advantage. This paper concludes that SMMEs could become more competitive by employing innovation.

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